

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CHOICE OF INFANT FEEDING PRACTICE AMONG MOTHERS AT SMVMCH, PUDUCHERRY

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Breastfeeding is a child's first barrier against death and disease, providing protection against respiratory infection, gastrointestinal illness, and other adverse health outcomes. Breastfeeding has also been associated with increased IQ, school attendance, as well as higher income in adult life. **Objective:** To assess the level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers. **Methodology:** The total number of 30 mothers were selected for this study. Multidimensional scale of perceived social support was used to assess the factors of choice of infant feeding among mothers. The design used for the present study was a Descriptive research design. **Result and Findings:** The finding revealed that majority, 21 (70%) of the mother had medium perceived support, 7 (23.3%) of the mother had high perceived support and 2 (6.7%) of the mother had low perceived support. **Conclusion-** The study findings concluded that there is significance association between the feeding method and nature of delivery among mothers where 'p' value is < 0.05.

Keywords: Breast feeding, mothers, infant feeding practice

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Introduction

Breastfeeding is a crucial aspect of a child's life, providing protection against diseases, promoting physical, mental, and cognitive development, and reducing the risk of various conditions. The World Health Organization recommends infants exclusively receive breastmilk for the first six months of life and consume nutritionally adequate foods for two years and beyond.

Breastfeeding fosters a stronger bond between mother and child, and is considered the gold standard for child nutrition. However, poor breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices, particularly in developing countries, contribute to malnutrition, a major cause of 3.8 million deaths and 35% of disease burden among those under five. Factors such as socioeconomic status, cultural beliefs, social support, education, work demands, age, care interventions, family pressures, and commercial advertising also influence breastfeeding decisions. The lack of necessary support for mothers to sustain breastfeeding has resulted in variable rates of breastfeeding worldwide.

Objectives

- To assess the level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers.
- To associate level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers with selected demographic variables.

Hypotheses

- H₁- There will be a significant association between the level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers with selected demographic variables.

Methodology

The research approach for this study employed a quantitative methodology with a descriptive research design to address the research question. The study was conducted at Sri Manakula Vinayagar Medical College and Hospital (SMVMCH). The target population consisted of all mothers, while the accessible population included mothers in SMVMCH, Puducherry, meeting specific inclusion criteria. A sample of 30 mothers was selected using a convenient sampling technique.

The inclusion criteria encompassed mothers admitted to or visiting the outpatient department (OPD) at SMVMCH who were willing to participate. Mothers who were ill during data collection were excluded. The data collection tool included two sections: demographic variables and the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS), which measures perceived social support from family, friends, and significant others. The MSPSS uses a 7-point Likert scale with scores categorized into low, medium, and high perceived support.

The tool's validity was ensured through expert review, and its reliability was established using the test-retest method, achieving a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.8$. Data collection involved informed consent, demographic data gathering, and MSPSS assessment to evaluate factors influencing infant feeding practices. Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage distribution) were used for demographic analysis and perceived social support levels, while inferential statistics (Chi-square test) examined associations between perceived support and selected demographic variables. The researcher-maintained confidentiality throughout the process.

Data collection Procedure

After obtaining formal permission, the researcher proceeded with data collection. Informed consent was obtained from mothers who were included in the study. The researcher used a convenient sampling technique to select 30 mothers who are admitted and from OPD in SMVMCH, Puducherry, who fulfilled the criteria. Demographic data was collected. Assessment was done using Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support on mothers regarding the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice. The investigator assured the study participants that the study information will be kept confidential.

Plan of data analysis

The collected data were coded and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive analysis included the use of frequency and percentage distribution to examine the demographic variables of mothers and assess the levels of perceived social support influencing their choice of infant feeding practices. Inferential statistics, specifically the Chi-square test, were employed to determine the association between levels of perceived social support and selected demographic variables, providing insights into the factors impacting mothers' feeding choices.

Result and Findings:

The majority of mothers (63.3%) were aged 26-30 years, with 20% aged 31-35 years and 16.6% aged 21-25 years. All participants (100%) were married. Regarding education, 60% were graduates, and 40% had completed higher secondary education. Most mothers (70%) belonged to the middle class, 16.6% to the high class, and 13.3% to the low class. In feeding methods, 73.3% practiced exclusive breastfeeding, while 26.6% used mixed or formula feeding. Regarding family type, 44.2% were in joint families, and 55.8% were in nuclear families. Most mothers (93.3%) had no chronic illness, while 6.7% had one. Neonatal complications were present in 16.7% of cases, with 83.3% reporting none. Birth weights were predominantly 2-2.5 kg (53.3%), with 33.3% in the 2-2.5 kg range. [Tab-1]

Table 1: Distribution of Demographic Variable of mothers.

S. No	Demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age		
	a) Under 21	0	0%
	b) 21-25	5	16.6%
	c) 26-30	19	63.3%
	d) 31-35	6	20%
2.	Marital status		
	a) Single	0	0%
	b) Married	30	100%
	c) Divorced	0	0%
3	Place of residence		
	a) Rural	12	40%
	b) Urban	18	60%
4	Education qualification		
	a) Primary education	0	0%
	b) Higher secondary	12	40%
	c) Graduate	18	60%
5	Financial status		
	a) High class	5	16.6%
	b) Middle class	21	70%
	c) Low class	4	13.3%

With regard to level of attitude the mean posttest level of attitude in the experimental group shows that in the experimental group all the women 10(100%) had positive attitude whereas in the control group only 1(10%) had positive attitude. This highlights attitude improved in the experimental group after the education programme more than control group. [Tab-2]

Table 2: Distribution of level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers

S.NO	LEVEL OF PERCEIVED SOCIAL SUPPORT	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENTAGE %
1.	Low perceived support	2	6.7%
2.	Medium perceived support	21	70%
3.	High perceived support	7	23.3%

The above table reveals the frequency and percentage-wise distribution of level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers. The finding revealed that majority, 21 (70%) of the mother had medium perceived support, 7 (23.3%) of the mother had high perceived support and 2 (6.7%) of the mother had low perceived support. [Tab-2]

Table 3: Mean, SD and mean% of level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers.

Overall	Level of awareness Score			
	Max. score	Mean	SD	Mean%
	84	59.76	11.007	71.14

The above table reveals mean, SD and mean% of level of perceived social support on the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers. The finding revealed that mean score of 59.76 with the SD of 11.007. The overall mean percentage is 71.14

Table 4: Association of level of patient perception on factors affecting gender role in nursing care with their selected demographic variables

S.NO	Demographic variables	Level of stress						X ² value
		Low		Moderate		High		
1	Age	N	%	N	%	N	%	X ² = 2.041 p = 0.839 (NS)
	a) Under 21	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	b) 21-25	1	3.3	3	10	1	3.3	
	c) 26-30	1	3.3	15	50	3	10	
	d) 31-35	0	0	3	10	3	10	
2.	Place of residence							X ² = 1.041 p = 0.684 (NS)
	a) Rural	1	3.3	8	26.7	3	10	
	b) Urban	1	3.3	13	43.3	4	13.3	
3.	Marital status							K
	a) Single	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	b) Married	2	6.7	21	70	7	23.3	
	c) Divorced	0	0	0	0	0	0	
4.	Education qualification							X ² = 0.201
	a) Primary education	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	b) Higher secondary	2	6.7	4	13.3	6	20	

	c) Graduate	0	0	17	56.7	1	3.3	p = 0.825 (NS)
5.	Financial status							
	a) High class	0	0	2	6.7	3	10	
	b) Middle class	1	3.3	18	60	2	6.7	

*P<0.05 - SIGNIFICANT; P<0.01 - HIGHLY SIGNIFICANT; K-CONSTANT

The above table shows that there is significance association between the feeding method and nature of delivery among mothers where ‘p’ value is < 0.05. There is no significance association among level of stress among mothers with between age, marital status, place of residence, education qualification, financial status, mother having chronic illness, neonatal complication and birth weight.

Conclusion

The present study assessed the factors influencing the choice of infant feeding practice among mothers at SMVMCH, Puducherry. The study findings concluded that there is significance association between the feeding method and nature of delivery among mothers where ‘p’ value is < 0.05.

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